

DETERMINATION OF SHEAR AND THE EFFECTS OF FIBER ORIENTATION DURING INJECTION OF A BMC COMPOUND

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ABSTRACT

The study presented in this article is a continuation of VETROTEX's initial research on BMC and ZMC manufacture in view of developing glass fibers that reduce the viscosity of injected compounds. The viscosity created by reinforcement is a considerable problem, as it has significant influence on how molds are filled and on the size of the injection press.

A reliable and representative method is needed to measure viscosity and to identify its most important parameters.

The results should make it possible to analyse shear's actual role as well as to determine the extensional behavior of the compound and thereby calculate the aspect ratios of glass fibers.

1. WHAT IS THE VISCOSITY OF A COMPOUND ?

Viscosity is a complex notion. Shear viscosity is created by friction (layer against layer and compound against walls), while extensional viscosity is created by the variations in cross-section that occur during passage through the CONVERGENT/DIVERGENT systems.

If η represents shear viscosity and λ represents extensional viscosity:

* for isotropic, homogenous or newtonian materials:

$$\lambda = 3 \eta$$

* whereas for anisotropic materials extensional viscosity can be more than 100 times greater than shear viscosity.

For extensional viscosity:

* the greater the degree of anisotropy, the higher the value of λ

* in the special case of compounds, λ has a high value because:

- fibers may be aligned with the flow

- the aspect ratios of the fibers' L/D amplify the effects of their orientation

Note: L and D mean length and average diameter respectively.

* the determination of λ makes it possible to define L/D

When expressing viscosities, η and λ vary with the shear rate according to the power law:

$$\eta = B \dot{\gamma}^{m-1}$$

where:

$\dot{\gamma}$ is the shear rate

B, m are constant for a given compound

$$\lambda = A \dot{\epsilon}^{n-1}$$

where:

$\dot{\epsilon}$ is the extension rate for surfaces during passage in convergent/divergent systems,

A, n are constant for a given compound,

$\dot{\epsilon}$ is related among others to $\dot{\gamma}$ [1], [2].

2. DEFINING THE DIFFERENT VISCOSITIES OF A COMPOUND

The BAGLEY and COGSWELL [3] and GIBSON [4] models are applied to determine η and λ and the viscosity parameters A, B, m and n.

2.1 Methodology (see annex and Figure 1)

* Injection at 50°C in:

- a convergent (extension and shear)
- followed by a capillary (shear)

* Choice of an angle α :

$\alpha = 60^\circ\text{C}$, which represents a compromise between:

- the most extensional regime possible which increases with α , in order to improve the accuracy of the extensional characteristics, or
- the emergence of dead zones which also increase with α (Figure 2).

* Capillary: exclusively shear regime

- work with shear rates ranging from 10,000 to 35,000 s^{-1}
- variations in capillary length from 0 to 150 mm, when diameter = 5 mm

2.2 Viscosity parameter calculation

* shear inside the capillary

- BAGLEY method (equations (1) and (2))

* shear and extension in the convergent

- COGSWELL/GIBSON method (equations (3) to (7))

3. SURPRISING RESULTS FOR SHEAR

The results concerning shear show that whatever:

- the filler content (from 170 to 270 parts of CaCO_3),
- the glass content by weight (from 15% to 25%),
- the glass fiber sizing used (A,B,C,D,E),
- the tex: 37.5, 75, or 1200 (direct roving),
- the fibers' chopped strand length (13 and 25 mm),

there exists a quasi-universal and highly significant relationship (Figure 3) between B and m:

$$B = 1.75 \cdot 10^4 \cdot e^{-10.08 m}$$

Thus η becomes a unique function of:

- the shear rate $\dot{\gamma}$
- the velocity profile of the flow represented by m

$$\eta = 1.75 \cdot 10^4 e^{-10.08 m} \dot{\gamma}^{m-1}$$

At low shear rates, the lower the value for m , the higher η becomes, while at a high shear rate of 23860 s^{-1} , all the viscosities are equal regardless of the value of m .

Note: All these results come from direct observation without any extrapolation outside of the shear range used for experimental purposes. The value of the exponent m is directly linked to the type of flow (Figures 4 and 5). When m is close to 1, the flow is newtonian. When m is close to 0, the flow is of the "plug" type with a flattened velocity profile.

* Meaning of the relationship $B = f(m)$

Viscosity and temperature are linked according to:

$$\eta = a e^{-bT} \quad [5]$$

where:

a, b are experimental constants,
 T is temperature.

In addition, it can be shown that:

$$m b_{\tau} = b \dot{\gamma} \quad [5]$$

where:

b_{τ} is defined with a constant shear stress,
 $b \dot{\gamma}$, with a constant shear rate.

In relationship with our own results and after identifying the terms, one obtains:

$$e^{-10.08 m} = e^{-b \dot{\gamma} T}$$

where:

$b \dot{\gamma} = m b_{\tau}$,
 $T = 323 \text{ K}$

This takes place as if $b \dot{\gamma}$ were constant and independent from $\dot{\gamma}$ in the entire range of shear rate variations.

Thus one obtains:

$$b_{\tau} = 3.1 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$$

These initial results require confirmation by a specific systematic study in order to better understand the role played by the exponent m in expressing B .

4. PRODUCT BEHAVIOR

4.1 Shear

We define the "short fiber content" as the weighted content of fibers smaller than 0.5 mm in relation to the total mass of the glass, *at the mixer outlet* during compound manufacture. The mixer has the effect of shortening the initial fiber length.

There is a relationship between the "short fiber content" and the type of flow when shear is concerned (see TABLE 1):

The higher the "short fiber content", the more the flow becomes pseudoplastic, with a low value for m .

The lower the value of m , the higher the viscosity, at a given shear rate.

The more a strand is sensitive to filamentisation and to abrasion, the higher its "short fiber content" will be.

m also varies according to glass content [6] (Figure 6).

These parameters must be taken into account when defining viscosities.

With a nominal content of 20%, a BMC compound's actual glass content may range from 18 to 22%. In this case, Figure 6 shows that for a given compound, m varies from 0.53 to 0.42, which represents viscosity fluctuations of over 10%. This can also have significant consequences on the setting of injection presses.

4.2 Extensional viscosity

Parameters A and n remain relatively stable, especially the exponent n which varies only slightly: between 0.5 and 0.7 (see Table 2)

$$\lambda = A \dot{\epsilon}^{n-1}$$

Although the extensional viscosity can be several dozens of times higher than the shear viscosity, the flow phenomenon in the molds that consumes most of the energy (due to the injection pressure) is still shear. The main advantage to determining parameters A and n relating to the extensional viscosity is that it gives access to the fibers' aspect ratios. The aspect ratios, when calculated using the BATCHELOR [7] method, are only slightly different from one fiber to another, but nevertheless seem fairly accurate (Figure 7).

Once again the glass content has an influence on the results. In the particular case shown in Figure 6, one can see that an increase in glass content causes increased interaction between fibers and therefore higher abrasion which in turn leads to a deterioration of the fibers' residual aspect ratios.

It should be noted here that the order of magnitude of the aspect ratios measured is concordant with the possible values for a tri-dimensional BMC compound with the standard glass content. In this case, according to GIBSON [8], L/D should fall between 30 and 50. As far as space requirement is concerned, L/D greater than 50 would imply an alignment of the fibers in one plane. This would begin to resemble SMC.

CONCLUSIONS

It is clear that the "short fiber content" of a BMC compound has a significant influence on the type of flow in the molds.

We have demonstrated that a universal law exists controlling shear, whatever the filler content, the glass content, the type of reinforcement, the chopped strand length, etc., and that the pseudoplasticity coefficient plays a fundamental role in this law.

This coefficient m , which is characteristic of the type of flow and directly related to the "short fiber content", alone determines the compound's behavior, for a given flow geometry and shear rate. We have seen that a newtonian flow profile, where m approaches 1, will consume less energy and therefore less pressure than a very flat profile where m is close to 0 (given that an increase in the "short fiber content" causes a decrease in m).

Moreover, the particular influence of m on the viscosity values results in an identical value for all of them, with a shear rate at 23860 s^{-1} , regardless of the type of glass or formulation studied.

The fibers' aspect ratios vary only slightly from one formulation to another and appear to be closely linked to volume limitations as well as to the fiber-to-fiber abrasion factor in a tri-dimensional compound such as BMC.

References

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ANNEX

$$P_c = \frac{2BL}{R_1} \left(\frac{1+3m}{4m} \right)^m \dot{\gamma}^m \quad (1)$$

P_c is the pressure drop in the capillary
 L, R_1 are respectively the length and radius of the capillary
 B, m are the viscous characteristics
 $\dot{\gamma}$ is the apparent shear rate at the walls

$$\dot{\gamma} = \frac{4Q}{\pi R_1^3} \quad (2)$$

Q is the flow rate

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \frac{\dot{\gamma} \sin \alpha (1 + \cos \alpha)}{4} \quad (3)$$

$\dot{\epsilon}$ is the extension rate
 α is the half angle of the convergent

$$P_{e1} = A \dot{\gamma}^n \left[\frac{2}{3n} \left(\frac{\sin \alpha (1 + \cos \alpha)}{4} \right)^n \left(1 - \left[\frac{R_1}{R_0} \right]^{3n} \right) + \frac{\phi(n, \alpha)}{4^n} \right] \quad (4)$$

A, n are the extensional characteristics
 R_0 is the radius of the die before the convergent

$$\phi(n, \alpha) = \int_0^\alpha (1 + \cos \beta)^{n-1} \sin^{n+1} \beta d\beta \quad (5)$$

$$P_{e2} = \frac{2B \dot{\gamma}^m \sin^3 \alpha}{3m \alpha} \left(\frac{1+3m}{4m} \right)^m \left[1 - \left[\frac{R_1}{R_0} \right]^{3m} \right] \quad (6)$$

P_{e1} is the pressure drop in the convergent due to the extension effect
 P_{e2} is the pressure drop in the convergent due to shear.

The procedure consists of defining the total load loss P_T

$$P_T = P_c + P_{e1} + P_{e2}$$

Defining P_T in relation to L/R_1 makes it possible to determine the value of P_T by extrapolation when L is nil, thus:

$$P_T = P_{e1} + P_{e2} = P_{ENT}$$

We can now determine the entry pressure P_{ENT} in the capillary for every shear rate. As a corollary, we can also determine the value of P_c for every shear rate and L/R_1 ratio. BAGLEY's logarithmic procedure then allows the immediate definition of parameters B and m .

Moreover, it can be demonstrated that:

$$A\dot{\epsilon}^n = \frac{P_{e1}}{\frac{2}{3n} \left[1 - \left[\frac{R_1}{R_0} \right]^{3n} \right] + \frac{\phi(n, \alpha)}{(\sin \alpha (1 + \cos \alpha))^n}} \quad (7)$$

Once B and m have been defined, P_{e2} can then be calculated for every value of $\dot{\gamma}$.

We can then determine the value of P_{e1} by subtraction, for every value of $\dot{\gamma}$ (or of $\dot{\epsilon}$)

$$P_{ENT}(\dot{\gamma}) - P_{e2}(\dot{\gamma}) = P_{e1}(\dot{\gamma})$$

Equation 7, expressed as a logarithm, makes it possible to determine n and then A .

The geometrical parameters R_0 and R_1 and α remain constant.

TABLE 1

Glass fiber sizing/tex	Glass content by weight (%)	Chopped strand length (initial) (mm)	m	Short fiber content (%)
A - 75 tex	16.9	13	0.13	27.9
B - 1200 tex	23.7	13	0.35	7.3
A - 37.5 tex	21.0	13	0.42	10.0
B - 1200 tex	17.8	25	0.45	6.5
B - 1200 tex	20.6	13	0.50	5.5
B - 1200 tex	15.2	13	0.59	5.9
C - 75 tex	20.0	13	0.59	3.2
D - 75 tex	20.2	13	0.73	4.7
E - 75 tex	20.3	13	0.89	2.5
Polyester resin with 220 weighted parts of CaCO ₃				

TABLE 2

Sizing/tex	Glass content by weight (%)	Chopped strand length (initial) (mm)	A	n	Aspect ratio (L/D)
A - 37.5 tex	21.0	13	1240	0.55	29.7
A - 75 tex	16.9	13	650	0.60	30.2
B - 1200 tex	23.7	13	1970	0.53	31.4
D - 75 tex	20.2	13	2250	0.49	31.7
C - 75 tex	20.0	13	470	0.68	32.5
B - 1200 tex	20.6	13	1650	0.54	32.6
E - 75 tex	20.3	13	1860	0.53	33.6
B - 1200 tex	15.2	13	1220	0.54	35.0
B - 1200 tex	17.8	25	990	0.60	36.7
<p>- Aspect ratio calculated at $\dot{\gamma} = 15,000 \text{ s}^{-1}$ - Polyester resin with 220 weighted parts of CaCO_3 (same formulation conditions as those used to determine the shear parameters).</p>					

Figure 1 : Exit of the convergence and die geometry for capillary flow

Figure 2 : Schematic showing features of flow pattern near to convergence

Figure 3 : Relationship between B and m for shear flow

Figure 4 : Velocity profile for a Newtonian flow through tubes

Figure 5 : Velocity profile for a pseudoplastic flow through tubes

Figure 6 : Relationship between m and glass content by weight (%)

Figure 7 : Relationship between aspect ratio (L/D) and glass content by weight (%)